

Pop_ID	<i>Trichogramma</i> species	Reproduction	Sampling date	Sampling location	Latitude	Longitude	Allee effect
bra_1	brassicae	sexual	13/07/2015	Aix en Provence	43.5917	5.4253	
bra_2	brassicae	sexual	13/07/2015	Aix en Provence	43.5917	5.4253	
cac_1	cacoeciae	asexual	20/05/2015	Banyuls sur mer	42.453894	3.087794	
cac_2	cacoeciae	asexual	21/06/2015	Grasse	43.660153	6.926492	
cac_3	cacoeciae	asexual	20/08/2015	Andon	43.77941	6.84057	
cac_4	cacoeciae	asexual	27/07/2015	Aime	45.548561	6.629682	X
cac_5	cacoeciae	asexual	27/07/2015	Aime	45.548561	6.629682	X
cac_6	cacoeciae	asexual	27/07/2015	Aime	45.548561	6.629682	
cac_7	cacoeciae	asexual	27/07/2015	Aime	45.548561	6.629682	
cac_8	cacoeciae	asexual	27/07/2015	Tours sur Meymont	45.670778	6.97181	X
cac_9	cacoeciae	asexual	13/08/2015	Courmes	43.79109	4.976422	X
cac_10	cacoeciae	asexual	30/04/2015	Beynost	45.832313	4.976422	X
cac_11	cacoeciae	asexual	22/06/2015	Rancé	45.951937	4.883082	
cac_12	cacoeciae	asexual	22/06/2015	Rancé	45.951937	4.883082	
cac_13	cacoeciae	asexual	30/04/2015	Rancé	45.951937	4.883082	
cac_14	cacoeciae	asexual	23/04/2015	Joué les Tours	47.351861	0.6613099	
cac_15	cacoeciae	asexual	14/06/2015	Dannemois	48.45733	2.486348	
cac_16	cacoeciae	asexual	14/06/2015	Moret sur Loing	48.35066	2.809645	
cor_1	cordubensis	asexual	20/05/2015	Banyuls sur mer	42.453894	3.087794	
cor_2	cordubensis	asexual	09/07/2015	La Pugère	43.74282	5.12722	
cor_3	cordubensis	asexual	20/08/2015	La Pugère	43.7471	5.12456	
eup_1	euproctidis	sexual	13/07/2015	Aix en Provence	43.5917	5.4253	
eup_2	euproctidis	sexual	13/07/2015	Aix en Provence	43.5917	5.4253	
eva_1	evanescens	sexual	13/08/2015	Castellaras	43.78393	6.83258	
eva_2	evanescens	sexual	20/07/2015	Estrablin	45.516941	4.962637	
pri_1	principium	sexual	13/08/2015	Gréolières	43.82627	6.90479	X
sem_1	semblidis	sexual	13/07/2015	Aix en Provence	43.5917	5.4253	
sem_2	semblidis	sexual	22/06/2015	Rancé	45.951937	4.883082	
sem_3	semblidis	sexual	22/06/2015	Rancé	45.951937	4.883082	X
sem_4	semblidis	sexual	14/06/2015	Dannemois	48.45733	2.486348	X

Table S1 : Sampling information and characterization of Allee effects for the 30 populations included in the study. In grey : population for which all replicates went extinct.

Figure S1: Time series of the 8 replicates for each of the 30 populations. Red boxes: populations characterized with an Allee effect.